

Electrochemical behaviour of 5-benzyl-4-(4'-methylphenyl)-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol by voltammetry

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Abstract : The electrochemical study of a thiotriazole compound, 5-benzyl-4-(4'-methylphenyl)-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol (TTA) was made with cyclic voltammetry (CV) and differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) using glassy carbon electrode (GCE) as working electrode and an Ag/AgCl reference electrode in the Britton- Robinson buffer. The best results for electrooxidation of TTA were obtained in basic media (in 10% ethanol-0.2 M NaOH). This compound display one irreversible oxidation peak, which is attributed to a dimerization process involving the formation of disulphide derivative (EC mechanism).

Keywords : Thiotriazole, electrochemical behaviour, glassy carbon electrode.

Recently, a number of publications have appeared on the electrochemical investigation of thiol (RSH) compounds¹. Thiotriazole compounds are of interest because of their broad applications in the area of pharmaceutical and agricultural chemistry. They are also used as models of sulphur metal proteins². Some electrochemical investigations on thiotriazole and thiadiazole have also been reported^{2,3}. On the other hand, 2-amino-5-mercapto-1,3,4-triazole was used to fabricate self-assembled monolayers on gold electrode for simultaneous determination of dopamine and uric acid⁴. In the present paper, the electrochemical oxidation of a synthesized reagent, TTA, in 0.2 M NaOH (10% ethanol) at GCE was investigated by DPV and CV.

Experimental

Reagents and solutions : All reagents were of analytical grade. TTA was synthesized as reported earlier⁵. The stock solution of TTA (10^{-2} M) was prepared in ethanol. Due to the low solubility of this compound in aqueous media, 10% v/v ethanol solutions were used for voltammetric studies. Britton-Robinson buffer was used for varying pH. Ethanol, CH₃COOH, H₃PO₄, H₃BO₃, NaOH, H₂SO₄, were obtained from Merck.

Electrodes and instrumentation : The Differential Pulse Voltammetry (DPV) and Cyclic Voltammetry (CV) were performed with a Metrohm Model 757 VA Computrance with

conventional three-electrode cell, Glassy Carbon Electrode (GCE) as the working electrode, Ag/AgCl as the reference and Pt wire as counter electrode. All voltammetric measurements were carried out at room temperature under argon. Before measurements, the working electrode was sequentially polished with graded alumina powder 10 μm (Merck), rinsed with doubly distilled water. The pH values were measured with pH meter Metrohm Model 744. The supporting electrolytes contained 10% ethanol used in all experiments.

Results and discussion

The crystal structure of thiol compounds corresponded to the thione form, but they showed thiol-thione tautomerism in solution (Scheme 1)⁶. Due to this TTA has oxidizable -SH group.

The pH dependence of the oxidation of TTA was studied in the pH range between 2 to 12 in Britton-Robinson buffer by DPV. The oxidation potential (E_p) decreases with

Scheme 1. Thiol-thione tautomerism of TTA.

Fig. 1. Differential Pulse Voltammograms in 10% ethanol-0.2 M NaOH at different concentration of TTA : (a) blank, (b) 10^{-5} , (c) 4.0×10^{-5} , (d) 6.0×10^{-5} , (e) 8.0×10^{-5} , (f) 1.0×10^{-4} , (g) 1.5×10^{-4} , (h) 2.0×10^{-4} , (i) 2.5×10^{-4} , (j) 3.0×10^{-4} , (k) 4.0×10^{-4} M.

increasing pH from 1.02 V (pH 2.03) to 0.655 V (pH 12.00). The voltammetric pK_a value of TTA was found to be about 7.00 from E_p -pH curves, which value is in good agreement with pK_a values of some triazoles².

The current (I_p) corresponding to the oxidation peak decreases between the pH range 2–6, becomes constant between pH 6–8 and then increases at alkaline pH. When basic supporting electrolyte is used, H^+ was easily released and the peak was sharp. Thus, 10% ethanol-0.2 M NaOH was selected as the optimum supporting electrolyte for all voltammetric studies. Fig. 1 shows the DP voltammograms for various concentrations of TTA from 2.0×10^{-5} to 4.0×10^{-4} in 10% ethanol-0.2 M NaOH. The peak current of TTA at the surface of GCE is linear up to 0.4 mM and is described by the equation $I (\mu A) = 32.87 C_{TTA} + 0.028$, $r = 0.998$, where $I (\mu A)$ is the oxidation peak current, C_{TTA} is the analyte concentration (mM), r is the correlation coefficient. The linear dependence of peak current with concentration indicates that the oxidation of TTA is diffusion controlled.

A typical cyclic voltammogram of TTA at various potential scan rates is shown in Fig. 2, obtained on the GCE in 10%

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammograms of 1 mM TTA at GCE scan rates : 10, 25, 50, 75, 100, 150, 200, 250, 300, 400, 500, 750, 1000 mV/s, supporting electrolyte : 10% ethanol-0.2 M NaOH.

ethanol-0.2 M NaOH. The positive scan shows a single irreversible oxidation peak at about 0.69 V, which is attributed to the oxidation of thiol leading to the disulphide formation (3,3'-dithiobis(5-benzyl-4-(4-methylphenyl)-4H-1,2,4-triazole), at 100 mV/s scan rate. No reduction peak corresponding to the oxidation was observed in the reverse scan. The linear increase in the oxidation peak current with the square root of the scan rate and log of peak current with log of scan rate gave a straight line with a slope of 0.49 ($\log I (\mu A) = 0.49 \log v + 0.317$, $r = 0.998$), indicating diffusion control process⁷.

Electrochemical oxidation of TTA leads initially to the generation of radical species with simultaneous H^+ release followed by a dimerization step (Scheme 2). So, it can be concluded that TTA can be oxidized irreversibly at GCE, following an EC mechanism.

Scheme 2. Electrooxidation mechanism of TTA in 10% v/v ethanol-0.2 M NaOH at GCE surface.

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